

FEMINIST PERSPECTIVE ON PERSONAL INFORMATION

PROTECTION LAW

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I. Introduction

With the acceleration of globalization and the rise of the relevance of data information integrity and personal security, security issues are placed at the forefront of theoretical research. However, China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take effect lacks a feminist perspective and does not include women's knowledge and experience in the study of security theory, making the law imperfect and need improvement. This paper will construct a feminist view of personal information security protection from a feminist perspective and inject feminist elements into the theory of personal information security. The full text is divided into five sections, as follows:

This paper first examines the personal information protection law that are about to take effect from a feminist perspective, combining feminism and national security. This section provides a basic overview of Feminism and Marxism, explaining the relationship between the two theories. Using the two leading existing schools of feminist theory - liberal feminism and Marxist feminism - the three perspectives - the state, the individual, and the corporation - are analyzed. The importance of social gender as a category of analysis in feminist theory is outlined.

The second part analyzes the problems in the existing laws from three perspectives: the state, the company, and the individual. These problems include the neglect of rights, the lack of data, and the neglect of the management of legal

persons, which have adverse effects and risks for national security, commercial companies, and individuals.

The third part is the focus of this paper, which makes suggestions and possible improvements to the personal information protection law that are about to take effect from a feminist perspective. The third part is to provide reasonable solutions to the state, enterprises, and individuals based on the issues raised in the second part and to improve the formulation of laws.

The last part is the conclusion. Research on the feminist view of personal information protection is still in the preliminary stage of exploration. In the process of practice, it can be used as a theoretical basis for exploring the improvement of personal information protection from a female perspective. However, it still faces many challenges and needs to go through a long process to genuinely address the neglect of feminist concerns, such as emotion and dignity, in the legislation.

II. Feminism and application

A. Marxism and Feminism

According to the book *Toward a Feminist Theory of The State* written by Catharine A. Mackinnon, Marxist theory argues that society is fundamental constructed of the relations people form as they do and make things needed to survive humanly. While Implicit in feminist theory is a parallel argument: the molding, direction, and expression of sexuality organizes society into two sexes:

women and men. This division underlies the totality of social relations. Sexuality is the social process through which social relation of gender are created, organized, expressed, and directed, creating the social beings we know as women and men, as their relations create society. In her book, she writes the women's movement focus upon attitudes, beliefs, and emotions as powerful components of social reality is criticized as formally idealist.¹ Feminists have often found that working-class movements and the left neglect the role of feelings and beliefs in a focus on institutional and material change, denigrate women in practice and in everyday life, and in general fail to distinguish themselves from any other ideology or group dominated by male interests, where justice for women is concerned. In her book, she says that most people in society think that Marxism is not concerned with the emotions that feminism is concerned with, but only with material things like money.

	Feminism	Marxism
Focus	sexuality	work
Exploited groups	women	workers
Belief	Rights (emotion, dignity)	Interests(money)

¹ Catharine Mackinnon, *Toward a Feminist Theory of the State*-Harvard University Press (1991), in THE PROBLEM OF MARXISM AND FEMINISM 323 (First Harvard University Press paperback edition, 1991 ed. 1989).

B. Different Schools of Feminism

Feminist theory has shown diverse qualities in the 20th century and has given rise to many theoretical schools. To be specific, there are liberal feminism, radical feminism, Marxist feminism, postmodern feminism, cultural feminism, ecofeminism, psychoanalytic feminism, and many other schools of thought. Among them, the representative liberal feminism and Marxist feminism.²

Liberal feminism is considered as the conservative school of feminism, whose theories focus on eliminating gender discrimination and fighting for equal rights for men and women, demanding the government to give men and women the same rights and opportunities so that both can compete equally, and demanding women to show themselves through personal struggle in political, economic, and cultural fields.³

Marxist feminism⁴ emerged during the same historical period, influenced by the historical materialism of Marx and Engels and the perspective of the weak and powerless groups on the margins of the world economy. Its basic claim is that gender discrimination is a concrete manifestation of social inequality, that this inequality is closely related to socio-economic inequality, that economic power determines women's lives, and that true women's emancipation requires women to gain economic independence.

² Na Zhao, *An Appraisal on the National Safety Under the Feminism*, 2010.

³ Christine Sylvester, *Feminist Theory and International Relations in a Postmodern Era* (1994).

⁴ J. Ann Tickner, *Gender in International Relations: Feminist Perspective on Achieving Global Security* (1992).

Radical feminism	Liberal feminism	Marxist feminism
The root cause of women's oppression is patriarchy	Eliminate gender discrimination	Inequality is caused by social and economic inequalities
Turning women from the oppressed to the oppressor	Equal rights for two genders and compete equally for opportunity	The economy determines the lives of women
Patriarchal society limits women's access to a variety of rights	Showcasing themselves in various fields through their personal efforts	Gaining economic independence for liberation

III. The States, the corporations, individual

A. States

In a way, liberal feminism can jeopardize national security because liberal feminism is only concerned with agreements made between individuals and

individuals⁵, not with whether such agreements will violate the law of the state. So, if it goes against the laws of the country, then it can be a threat to the security of the country.

But in another way, liberal feminism is again trying to dismantle the concept of national security. National security is valued now because it is a patriarchal society that is full of competition and violence.⁶ But liberal feminism proposes to build a society where women are in power, and because of liberal feminism, there is much less competition and violence among women, and they are more inclined to work with each other in solidarity and harmony. In such a society, where every woman fully asserts her freedom, the world would be a better place and national security would not be a major political and military concern.

However, Marxist feminism believes that allowing every woman to exercise her freedom and achieve a better world presupposes that society needs to modify many realistic settings to achieve certain conditions so that the whole world is in the same order, in the same economic and political state.⁷ At the same time, Marxist feminism can be dissolved by creating a world government in which different countries have uniform standards. The construction of a world government does not conflict with the multiple women's groups of liberal

⁵ Swati Parashar, J. Ann Tickner & Jacqui True, Revisiting gendered states : feminist imaginings of the state in international relations, in *Masculine Allies And Feminist Change* 225 (2018).

⁶ Petrus Farneubun, *Feminist Critiques against Traditional Approaches to Security*, *Global & Strategis* 22 (2015).

⁷ Valerie Bryson, *Feminist political theory: An introduction* (1992).

feminism, because the world government attempts to establish a unified condition so that the various small groups can communicate and cooperate effectively, as well as make full use of liberal, but this vision is difficult to achieve.

Marxism and feminism are both idealisms, but realism is concerned with the facts of reality rather than the different genres. To be specific, there is a conflict between Huawei device manufacturers and Alibaba advertisers is a fact, a realist description. Realism needs idealistic commentary⁸, and needs to use feminism and Marxism, etc. as a yardstick to measure this fact and give an opinion. Realism would be the equivalent of a news report claiming that there is some kind of factual situation of monopoly of personal freedom in a realistic situation, at which point if one were to use liberal feminist values to comment on it, that comment would certainly be negative. And they try to adjust to this, to think about how feminism can intervene, how it can interfere with this, so that this can be adjusted back to a state of freedom. How to get from the real state to the ideal state? This requires intervention. It is as if in order to make a plant lush, one needs to adjust factors such as sunlight, water, distance between plants, etc. Protecting rights and interests, etc. is a means of intervention to achieve an idealistic state.

B. Corporations

Nowadays, more and more e-commerce platforms are advertising between customers and merchants, basically most of them are advertising according to

⁸ Mordecai Roshwald, Realism and Idealism in Politics, Vol. 46, No. 2 Pi Gamma Mu, International Honor Society in Social Sciences 8 (1971).

women's needs and aesthetics, helping some merchants to recommend their goods to customers, which can be considered as advertising for women as a group.

Marxist feminists believe that, in a sense, this practice is a kind of PUA for women, exploiting their dignity and emotions⁹ so that they can profit from selling products. A previous advertisement for a face pack is an example. In this ad, a woman is told by a colleague at work that her skin is not delicate because she did not use face pack. The woman then buys and uses the face pack recommended by her colleague, which is this item. After a few days of use, the woman is walking down the street and many people turn around to gaze at her glowing skin. Marxist feminism sees this ad as a way for the e-commerce platform to take advantage of women's self-esteem, which cares about what others think of them, and their emotions, which are focused on their appearance, to tempt women to spend money, a form of control over women.

On the other hand, from a liberal feminist standpoint, many commercials such as Double 11 and 618 are designed for women, which is a good thing. They believe that the advent of the consumer era, where women have the power to freely dispose of money, and these commercials by e-commerce platforms provide women with many options, is the result of the world's increased attention to women and the unprecedented expansion of the importance of women.¹⁰

⁹ Catharine Mackinnon, *supra* note 1.

¹⁰ Swati Parashar, J. Ann Tickner, and True, *supra* note 5.

C. Individuals

Liberal feminists are more inclined to protect all the possibilities of the individual, the so-called fundamental rights, such as various freedoms (freedom of expression, freedom of correspondence, etc.). These freedoms ensure that people have a variety of possibilities for self-development. The above is the liberal way of thinking.¹¹ Liberal feminism is about just guaranteeing everyone's freedom, as long as it's a matter of everyone being able to do what they want to do and say what they want to say. They do not care whether the matter is in accordance with public order and morality. As long as the matter is done of one's own will, even if that will be to be a slave, that is fine. Liberalism generally deconstructs away things like public order and morality, which means they analyze what the root of these things are and then disavow the thing itself. Liberal feminism would argue that as long as that person thinks the thing is free, it's good. But Marxism would argue that freedom is shaped. It's like for people who deliver, they are free to keep accelerating and eventually die in a car accident. But this seemingly free act, Marxist feminism believes is actually forced to do so by a combined force generated by the app, the people of the American group, the customers, including society. It's the equivalent of those black people who were born slaves, who didn't know there was any other way of life in the world. Assuming they are given freedom, they don't quite understand what to do to achieve it.

¹¹ Christine Sylvester, *supra* note 3.

Marxist feminists, who are usually consequentialists, are concerned with social rights, such as employment rights, minimum income guarantees, etc. From a Marxist perspective, the world is not a place where people can get the life they want if they are guaranteed basic freedoms. Rather, in conclusion, some social conditions and order need to be guaranteed. They believe that there must be material prerequisites for freedom to be possible.¹² Marxist feminism believes that the world needs a variety of foundations that must be secured in order for everyone to achieve freedom. And when someone does something that is not in accordance with public order and morality, even if it is of his own will, Marxist feminism believes that this is also bad. Marxist feminists would set what they consider to be a reasonable standard for society (the idea that being a slave would not make a good life for the person, even if the person wanted to be a slave), which is the public order and good customs mentioned in Chinese law. Marxist feminism believes that being a slave is a violation of public order and good customs, and a violation of general moral standards.

IV. Existing problems

In the context of the rapid development of the global digital economy, the increasingly intense game of data control and dominance in the international community, and the accelerated cultivation of data element markets in all countries, the China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take

¹² J. Ann Tickner, *supra* note 4.

effect will soon be in the public eye.¹³ The law provides clear rules on the handling of personal information, individual rights and obligations of processors, supervision and management, and legal liability, establishing a basic framework for the protection of personal information rights and interests and the orderly and free flow of personal information in the digital era. However, there are still some imperfections in the law that need to be improved, which can be analyzed at the level of the state, the corporation, and the individual, as well as from a uniquely feminist perspective.

A. Rights or Interests

First, the protection of all the interests in the personal information protection law that are about to take effect is imperfect. For individuals, based on the feminist view, interests are the money-related interests that Marxists are concerned with. They exclude national security, personal feelings and dignity, which are all equally important, from consideration.¹⁴

At the national level, protecting interests is not the same as protecting the security of the state. If the whereabouts data of some government officials is violated, it is equivalent to harming their personal information as well as the security of the country. Essentially, if from a philosophical point of view, if no one's personal privacy has been violated, national security is not violated. As an

¹³ Rogier Creemers et al., China's Draft "Personal Information Protection Law" (Full Translation), Long-awaited legislation on personal data released for public comment (2020).

¹⁴ Catharine Mackinnon, *supra* note 1.

example, each country has its own critical information infrastructure. They are critical to national security because in a state of war, the elimination of critical information infrastructure can quickly cripple the country. Some unscrupulous individuals have gained access to how to cripple this country's critical information infrastructure¹⁵ to undermine its security by violating each individual's information. These criminals obtain additional information about individuals that is generally not useful to them in business, but they have a natural tendency to collect additional information that they feel may come in handy later (from a profit perspective, recording where a government official goes does not cost the his/her money, but it compromises his/her personal rights and the national security. But in the other case, if these government officials authorize consent to these violations, then their own individual rights are not harmed, but the security of the country is threatened. Then in that case, it would be the equivalent of these government officials harming the security of the country, and no longer these people who are collecting personal information. There is also a situation where these unscrupulous people use the travel data of government officials to cheat them out of money, which is the worst kind of harming an individual's interests by violating his personal data, as well as his personal rights and the security of the country. ¹⁶

¹⁵ Karry Lai, Primer: China's draft Personal Information Protection Law, IFLR (2021).

¹⁶ Tajdar Jawaid, Privacy vs National Security, Volume 68 University of Dallas, TX, USA 7 (2020).

It would be more beneficial for business enterprises to assume that all interests are beneficial and monetized. But there is also the possibility of some kind of disorderly competition. To be specific, there are equipment vendors like Apple¹⁷ and Huawei¹⁸, who prefer to protect the personal information of users very well. And they do not like to make it a price in the pure sense, because these device vendors want to protect the privacy of their customers, to privacy as a selling point, so that people to buy their devices. But if one assumes that as a distributor or advertising platform like Alibaba, they do not like to get personal data is required to charge. Because Alibaba is equivalent to a middleman between customers and merchants, he wants to get personal data from customers for free, then process it for some series of summarized analysis, and finally sell this processed data (such as summarizing some customer shopping characteristics and preferences, etc.) to merchants like Taobao, and then earn money from the merchants.¹⁹ Assuming I am a merchant on Taobao, the core reason I would pay Alibaba is that Alibaba will bring me customers because Alibaba can direct customers to merchants for spending based on their personal information. So simply standing on the money, a lot of things are not solved. Equipment vendors and advertisers have completely different, even opposing, ideas about the use and protection of personal data, which can lead to a kind of disorderly competition.

¹⁷ Apple Privacy, .

¹⁸ HUAWEI Privacy, .

¹⁹ Saikat Guha, Bin Cheng, & Paul Francis, *Privad: Practical Privacy in Online Advertising*.

For the individual, only rights and money are mentioned, without taking into account the emotional dignity of the individual, which is exactly what feminists value so much.²⁰ And the matter of hurting people's feelings itself is not something that can be measured in terms of money. The point is not to have a business model that is the kind of thing that makes money by hurting people's emotion and dignity. Some ads induce social emotions to convince more people to buy their products, but often the emotions they induce are not the positive emotions like confidence and dignity, but the negative emotions of fear and vanity, which is not good for society.

B. Missing data

The second problem with China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take effect is that it only mentions the protection of existing personal data, but is still missing some important information generation.

For nations, a lot of people's rights exist based on the existence of certain underlying data. In other words, if researchers are going to say that a person have political rights, such as the right to vote, freedom of movement, etc., then they need to look at whether the data for the expression of those political rights exist.²¹ If they don't exist, even if he is said to have political rights, they are actually fake. It is as if the right of residence in the real sense now is actually a social welfare of the place the person belongs to, that is, generally speaking, it is not a rule that you

²⁰ Catharine Mackinnon, *supra* note 1.

²¹ Catherine Ignazio & Lauren Klein, *Data Feminism* (2020).

are not allowed to live somewhere, but there are restrictions on education and medical care for non-locals. If we look into this issue, the logic given by the education department is that it was not expected that so many people would come to Beijing in the first place. But the essence of not anticipating so many people is a lack of data. This is something that can be predicted, for how many people will move to Beijing and how many people will flow out of Beijing, and this is something that modern data science can provide. Missing data includes education, which is attached to the household registration, and also health care. The same is true for medical data, like what kind of hospitals will have how many people coming and when. If these data existed, it would make a lot more sense.

For commercial companies, missing some data can cost them some benefits. Companies are theoretically supposed to develop and offer products according to the needs of their customers,²² like how many people are willing to eat spicy food and how many are not. If this data were generated, the distribution of commerce would be a little more rational. Commercial companies are essentially resource deployment, providing community services, whether it's grocery shopping, haircuts, or meals. The current business model is imperfect. To be specific, the taste of Coca-Cola may be a median value of people's taste around the world, but there is no Chinese market to investigate the median value of Chinese taste. No one is doing this or don't know if there is or no one is doing this survey, this is the

²² Esen Gurbuz, *Theory of New Product Development and Its Applications* (2018).

lack of data. It is not very difficult to count the data of everyone's needs, and modern data science can solve this problem. Due to the lack of basic data for all people,²³ companies can only guess when deciding what kind of store to open and where to open. They can only make decisions by knowing what the GDP of the area is like and what the population is. So, when TAL Education Group found out how much the GDP per capita increased in the region and how much the population grew, it was time to open a store. On the other hand, let's say someone in a certain area says we want to have Mathematical Olympiad and English training institutions here, but the proposal is not accepted because the population or GDP per capita does not reach the target. It is unscientific and unjustified that companies now decide whether to open a store and where to open a store based on data like GDP and population, not on what people really want. There will be situations such as less people in this area, but there is demand, and more people in that area, but there is no demand. So, this kind of decision model will actually have a very high failure rate for commercial companies. And it is very difficult for a commercial company to design a questionnaire to investigate the needs or preferences of the population. But if the government has this kind of basic data of the whole population, it will be good to solve this problem. Nowadays, many community services are missing, and commercial services are not corresponding. People in Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou actually has a lot of demand for the

²³ Derek du Preez, Government's lack of data and performance monitoring leads to "crisis-cash-repeat" cycle for funding public services, *diginomica.com* (2019).

cultural field²⁴ (such as drama, musicals), and there are definitely not enough companies in the cultural field in these areas. On the other hand, students in the Central Academy of Drama and Beijing Film Academy are often unemployed not long after graduation.²⁵ Suppose the owner of some commercial companies originally opened a fast-food restaurant, if you don't give these companies some data support, he can't imagine how to open a drama store. Because people tend to think linearly,²⁶ that is, if you open a hot pot restaurant, you can open a million more, but if you ask this person to open a drama store, he thinks it is unbelievable. However, people's needs are not linear. The demand is from ordinary people, and opening a store is from the boss. Business companies think in a different way than ordinary people. Then if the data of ordinary people can be given to commercial companies, they will get some basic some information. In this way, it would be helpful to the country, to the common people and to the commercial companies, so it is necessary to generate data, and this is how feminism can rediscover the world.

For each person, the lack of data means that some aspect of people is neglected, and the result of neglect is that interests or rights are violated, such as

²⁴ Sisi Liang & Qingfang Wang, *Cultural and Creative Industries and Urban (Re)Development in China* (2020).

²⁵ Toby Miller, *Goodbye to Film School: Please Close the Door on Your Way Out*.

²⁶ Bart de Langhe, Stefano Puntoni, & Richard Larrick, *Linear Thinking in a Nonlinear World*, *Harvard Business Review* (2017).

personal safety.²⁷ The issue of femicide in Mexico is a case in point. It rose to global visibility in the mid-2000s with widespread media coverage about the deaths of poor and working-class women in Ciudad Juárez. Between 1993 and 2005, nearly four hundred of poor and working-class women in Ciudad Juárez were murdered, with around a third of those murders exhibiting signs of exceptional brutality or sexual violence. Convictions were made in only three of those deaths. In 2009 a report pointed out that one of the reasons that the issue had yet to be sufficiently addressed was the lack of data.²⁸ So in this case, the missing of data might cause the security of individual.

C. Natural person and Legal person

China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take effect lacks provisions for legal persons. For the nations, the missing addition of the legal person will cause the security problems for the countries.²⁹ There is a lot of data that does not belong to any natural person, such as weather data that belongs to the state or the Meteorological Bureau, a legal person. Because the state statistics out this data, you do not have the power to control this data. The data of individual households are personal, but once the state aggregates and counts these data, these data do not belong to the individual. It is unlikely that an individual will be able to obtain such data because it is not attributed to any natural person.

27 Brooke Auxier et al., *Americans and Privacy: Concerned, Confused and Feeling Lack of Control Over Their Personal Information*, PEW RESEARCH CENTER (2019).

28 Ignazio and Klein, *supra* note 21.

29 *Best Practices On Beneficial Ownership For Legal Persons*, (2019).

In addition, ocean data, such as how foreign submarines can bomb China, can be used as a war data, as well as weather data. To be specific, another country can use the data from the weather bureau to predict that there will be an ocean current, and it can wait for that ocean current, and then it can rush to the seashore of the hostile country, and then he can drop nuclear weapons on that country. Now the natural person does not have control of a lot of personal data,³⁰ like if the NSA gets a terrorist's signal, such as his calls to other people, the terrorist, as a natural person, does not have access to this data. This data does not belong to the terrorist as a natural person, but to the NSA as a legal person, so negligence in regulating legal persons can be detrimental to national security.

With regard to the corporations, since the concept of legal person has been constructed, it can no longer be ignored. Essentially, all legal persons are made up of natural persons behind them, but since legal persons have a separate personality right, companies are using legal persons to escape their responsibilities.³¹ Because a legal person can make it difficult for the government to figure out where the source of control is, this means that it is possible to design a company, the superior of this company (responsible for controlling this company) is still a company, and then further up is still a company. It can be nested, and it can contain different countries. It's like this company is in Ireland,

³⁰ Brooke Auxier et al., *supra* note 27.

³¹ G20 Research Group, *G20 High Level Principles on the Liability of Legal Persons for Corruption* (2017).

his parent company is in the United States, then the parent company is in Switzerland, then the parent company is in Hong Kong, then the parent company is in Dubai, then the parent company is in China. The end result is that the government can't figure out which natural person is controlling the legal entity. In this case, if the corporate company is not regulated, it will allow some companies to achieve the purpose of evading responsibility.³² For the government level, they are also easy to regulate this matter. Simply put, if Didi does something bad, the government can hold Didi,³³ the legal entity, accountable. Otherwise, it would be quite troublesome to know who is in control behind Didi. It is very difficult to hold a natural person accountable after Didi has done something illegal, but it is much easier to hold a legal entity accountable by directly investigating Didi's legal entity.

The lack of regulation of legal persons is something that does not affect individuals much. But theoretically speaking, if mutually hostile countries drop bombs also threaten the lives of natural persons. But all security issues are an expectation. If a person is worried about the security of his/her home, that means that there is a possibility that he/she will be stolen by a thief in the future, not that he/she is in his/her present state. It simply means that if the legal person is added to the regulation, these expectations are well handled. Otherwise, it is difficult to deal with these expectations like security. As a company, the government can let

³² Charles Doyle, *Corporate Criminal Liability: An Overview of Federal Law* (2013).

³³ BBC News, *Didi shares fall on reports China is planning penalties* (2021).

it do something to prepare for the long term, that is, let Didi, a legal person to protect some kind of national security is reasonable, the production of a large number of mechanisms is reasonable. But it's not reasonable to have a natural person create a security mechanism. In addition, because the person may be in the company or may leave the company, so there is no way to implement in a natural person, but if implemented in a company, you can require the company to do some kind of security settings and so on. If people in hotel ask him to turn on the air conditioning, people can ask work as a legal entity, but to implement it to a certain employee, it will not be possible to implement it when the employee is off work. When it comes to legal responsibility, we have to abstract it, and abstracting it to the hotel is enough, so we can save our time. We ask the hotel to have air conditioning on the line, and then the specific company's internal legal representative to arrange a specific person to do this. In short, this becomes a problem for the legal person to solve internally. Otherwise, people, such as which employee should be responsible for turning on the air conditioning, we do not know. And if it is specified clearly, it is a burden. What if the company changed its employees? In short, it causes a lot of trouble when it comes to natural persons, and it's less trouble when it comes to legal persons.

V. Solutions

There are various deficiencies in the existing China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take effect, and the negligence of these problems

can bring bad effects to the country, enterprises, or individuals. In order to improve these deficiencies, the following solutions are available for each of the problems in the law mentioned above.

A. Data Rights

In order to solve this problem, a right to data needs to be constructed. The following will explain what rights are included when such a right need to be constructed, how this right can be established, and what laws are related to it.³⁴

The data itself is the object of the right. Anything that can have a purpose attached to it is a subject, anything that has no purpose of its own is an object. The object is the tool or vehicle that helps the subject to realize its will. The matter of who owns anonymized data is still uncertain. It's not just that it has its own necessity, the UN human rights manual also says that data should be a right not an entitlement, a human right and not a money issue. Property rights are interests, human rights are rights, and property rights are opposed to human rights. Property rights are property properties, which are interests. The UN human rights handbook considers that there is personal data and there is non-personal data, and it considers that some data is related to people and some data is not related to people, but in fact both data and information are so.³⁵

34 Theresa L. Harris & Jessica M. Wyndham, Data Rights and Responsibilities: A Human Rights Perspective on Data Sharing, Vol. 10(3) 334–337 *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics* (2015).

35 Li Yongjian, Theoretical Construction of Personal Data Rights System, *Journal of Graduate School of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences* (2019).

If data rights are protected too much, it is not convenient for business owners to earn money. Advertisers like Alibaba would not be able to gain access to their customers' privacy, and in turn would not be able to provide services to their customers well. So, we have to consider the impact on commercial companies, the impact on national security, and the impact on individuals when we build this right. The impact on the bosses is that if this right is constructed, the bosses will not be able to carry on their business very well. In the UN article "*Government Policy for the Internet Must Be Rights-Based and User-Centred*", it is stated that the right system is built to maintain the balance of privacy transactions³⁶, that is, while the bosses are doing business, their personal privacy is also protected. The solution I gave out just tried to address the protection of personal data privacy and did not propose how to protect the boss to do business.

So, for this UN article, the right to data is divided into two parts, one part is free expression and the other is personal privacy. There should be a balance between these two parts, but apart from these two, the rest is property rights, and that's not to be considered. Just don't consider what the company side thinks. The UN article feels that there is a contradiction between the state and the individual, and that the state wants to protect national security. But individuals want to have individual rights. To be specific, a part of the people in North Africa wants to be able to express themselves freely in cyberspace, but the government does not

³⁶ Wafa Ben-Hassine, *Government Policy for the Internet Must Be Rights-Based and User-Centred*.

allow them to express themselves freely in the name of national security, this is the contradiction point. The right to data is constructed to promote a balance between national security and individual rights, and between national security and the free market.³⁷ So the key to the problem is where this balance lies.³⁸ If it is to protect national security, then a principle of necessity should be established. However, not every individual's privacy will be related to national security. There needs to be a strict definition of which individual rights are related to national security. There should be a balance in it. This includes commercial companies as well. Business companies may be doing business in a way that violates the law, but they should move in a direction that better protects the rights of individuals, in other words, in a 5- or 10-year period, so that they can adjust their privacy policies to a business model that does not rely on privacy and limits the expression of users,³⁹ but must convert to a model that protects human rights. and then also be able to do business in a model that protects human rights. These can be turned into a series of legal provisions, such as if the government wants to prove that this individual right is a matter of national security, it has to provide evidence. Commercial companies will have to adapt their business models within a few years, and that's the solution.

B. Investigation and collection of basic data

³⁷ Id.

³⁸ Tajdar Jawaid, *supra* note 16.

³⁹ Stacy-Ann Elvy, *Paying For Privacy And The Personal Data Economy*.

For the country, the solution to the data deficit is to collect basic information about the entire population, a move that makes sense for companies to help them meet specific needs, such as what a woman really wants to wear. The core appeal of the current advertising campaign is "people will look down on you if you don't dress like this", which basically gives women a negative sentiment.⁴⁰ Because existing commercial companies believe that people are more likely to buy based on this negative sentiment.⁴¹ But if the government can give the commercial companies positive individual-based data,⁴² like women's bodies actually have different data. In other words, if the government could give a substantial set of sizing, that is, what size of clothes each person should actually wear. The government collects some data and then formulates something a little more accurate for each person. It is the data now, such as large size small size, from 0 to 12, are linear. But it is possible that some people have a longer upper body, shorter lower body, some people have wider shoulders, some people have thin shoulders. In fact, it is not yet possible to make the clothes fit. Commercial companies have no incentive to make clothes that don't fit, but they also don't have the energy to take the time and effort to collect this data and figure out if it fits. After giving this data compulsion, it instead makes the commercial company better at selling its stuff. The commercial company has two possibilities. One is

⁴⁰ Christine Sylvester, *supra* note 3.

⁴¹ Joe Panepinto, Brands Shouldn't Believe Everything They Read About Themselves Online, *Harvard Business Review* (2018).

⁴² Kim Davis, *From sentiment to empathy: understanding how customers feel*, MarTech (2020).

that he does some basic work, such as doing a figure data survey or something. Suppose let the commercial company spend 20 million to do the data collection is able to do. But after doing this, the revenue and spend 20 million to scare consumers to say "you do not wear my clothes, everyone looks down on you" compared to the latter is obviously easier to earn money. But commercial companies are actually not averse to getting a good fit, it's just not cost effective for them. But if the state does the collection of basic data, given to commercial companies, all the companies in China can get this data, and commercial companies can instead do better business activities. So, it's a valuable thing for individuals, for business companies, and for the country. And this basic personal information data may enable some market segments to emerge. That is, in theory, the company does not need to make all the numbers of the clothes, only to find their own special market,⁴³ such as BM small size clothes market is designed specifically for petite girls. That can also have a marketplace for plus-size clothes, specifically made for girls with fuller figures. If this is done, it will be beneficial not only for the government, but also for commercial companies and individuals. For commercial companies, in the future they all need to have the ability to mine data on the government's published data platform. The only ability they have now is the ability to scare consumers. If the government doesn't provide such basic data now, commercial companies will have to rely on a variety of deceptive

⁴³ Indeed Editorial Team, Business Markets: Definition, Types and Examples (2021).

practices to make money. If more detailed data were available, commercial companies could provide services tailored to individual consumer needs.⁴⁴ This problem exists in almost all fields, like how can a mask fit; how many people should be in a car; what should be the height of a car going in. All of this basic data revolves around the people themselves, and the core is a data model of what all Chinese people should be like. Now Eurocode appears in the Chinese market itself is a problem. A lot of European data is very fine, so that the clothes Europeans wear very well-fitting and good-looking, Chinese people wearing it will not. But this is obviously the government's lack of basic data collection, and some visionary business companies over in Europe did this.

C. Adding legal person into the law

The third area for improvement in China's Personal Information Protection Law that are about to take effect is to include legal persons in the legislation so that they have the same rights as natural persons and are subject to the same regulation. Didi has given top national secrets of urban mapping data to the United States, a matter that has seriously jeopardized China the Internet Information Office has the responsibility to pursue Didi companies.⁴⁵ In this case, Didi company will be responsible as a legal person, for the state and the government will be very convenient management.

⁴⁴ Esen Gurbuz, *supra* note 22.

⁴⁵ Raymond Zhong, *China's Crackdown on Didi Is a Reminder That Beijing Is in Charge*, *The New York Times* (2021).

VI. Conclusion

The personal information protection law will fundamentally change data protection practices in China in 2021. However, the law is not perfect. This paper suggests that the law will introduce several issues. Meanwhile, the solution is not perfect either. In the solution of rights and interests, this study only considers the balance between national security and individual rights in the construction of data rights and does not stand to consider the position of commercial companies. This deficiency will now be taken into account by incorporating how to balance between commercial companies and national security and between individual rights and commercial companies.

In the aspect of personal privacy management, the conflict between advertisers and device vendors still has not been reasonably solved. The device vendor wants to protect the user's privacy to the maximum extent, but the advertiser wants to obtain the customer's privacy and handle it, and finally understand the customer's personal preferences to maximize their business interests. If the government wants to resolve this conflict, it needs to balance advertisers and equipment vendors. Imagine a situation where advertisers in other countries will win if there is an invasion of foreign cultures into their own country, and equipment vendors will win if there is a rapid change in technology development. Because the use of equipment is not limited to one country but can be in multiple countries, the equipment vendor can have a global voice, but the

advertiser may only have a voice within the country because different countries have different cultural backgrounds and advertisers are making ads in different ways.